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The enzyme patterns of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota fungi reveal their different functions in soil.

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Abstract

Keywords:
Saprotrophic fungi; C-Cycle; soil; metabolic adaptability; mycelium; enzymatic activity

The enzyme profile of a series of fungal isolates belonging to Ascomycota and Basidiomycota was analysed for a better understanding of the functional significance of their changes in soil with a specific focus on the carbon cycle. Two synthetic populations of Ascomycota and Basidiomycota isolates were compared on the basis of their enzymatic profiles. The activities of twenty-five enzymes extracted from the mycelium of pure fungal colonies were quantified in microplates using fluorogenic substrates. The enzyme activities were divided by the dsDNA content of each fungal colony and subjected to multivariate analysis. Ascomycota and Basidiomycota differed significantly ($P=0.0001$) in enzyme profile. Ascomycetes showed a broader enzymatic profile than Basidiomycetes. In the latter, seven out of the twenty-five enzyme activities detected in Ascomycetes were absent, including the enzymes of phosphorus and sulphur metabolisms and alpha-galactosidase. To the contrary, many enzymes responsible for plant polysaccharide degradation, such as alpha-galactosidase, beta-mannosidase or xilosidase were detected in the isolates of both fungal phyla. This indicates likely underestimated ability of Basidiomycetes to degrade plant polysaccharides, apart from their specific ability to decompose lignin. To the contrary, the widest enzyme profile of Ascomycota and their highest enzymatic inter- and intra-genus variability indicates their higher adaptability to metabolize different crop residues and litters.

1. Introduction

Saprotrophic fungi are key functional regulators in terrestrial ecosystems and are the most involved organisms in the C-cycle in which they play both a direct and indirect role. The primary function of saprotrophic fungi is to decompose plant residues, wood as well as any organic material (Fukasawa and Matsukura, 2021; Kyaschenko et al., 2017). This implies high production of an extensive set of plant cell walls polysaccharide-degrading and ligninolytic enzymes (Rytioja et al., 2014; Van Den Brink and De Vries, 2011); so much so that fungal exploitation for the extraction of degrading enzymes at an industrial level is very extensive and has reached high technological levels (Østergaard and Olsen, 2011).

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The extensive chromosomal polymorphisms resulting from chromosomal rearrangements in fungi generate substantial genome plasticity compared to other eukaryotic organisms (Mehrabi et al., 2017). This evolutionary advantage explains the largest adaptation of fungi towards different host plants (Mehrabi et al., 2017) and litters, and even towards various types of plastic polymers (Okal et al., 2023). Furthermore, it indicates a great ability in saprotrophic fungi to modify the enzyme pool (Zukiewicz-Sobczak et al., 2016) which contributes to the wide intraspecies variability of fungi and their strong adaptation to different environments (Dietzel et al., 2019).

For example, soilborne fungi increase their metabolic specialization towards a host plant becoming opportunistic pathogens when the same crop returns to the same soil and the soil microbial balance is compromised by intensive agricultural practices (Brader et al., 2017). Nevertheless, in natural ecosystems, soil fungi provide source material for soil organic matter through their beneficial relationship with plants (Jørgensen et al., 2022) because a large part of soil fungi can colonize roots and establish a commensal or mutualistic relationship with plants by promoting growth and protecting roots (Fu et al., 2015).

Enzyme activities are considered the main indicator of soil function and soil health (Gianfreda and Ruggiero, 2006; Merino et al., 2016; Piotrowska-Długosz et al., 2022) and are largely used for estimating key biogeochemical processes such as C- and N-cycles (Shi, 2010). They are among the most commonly used indicator of land use and widely adopted for evaluating the impact of climate change on soil processes (Liao et al., 2023; Meena and Rao, 2021). Although soil microbial community composition has been associated with specific enzyme activities and soil carbon chemistry (Li et al., 2019), the relationship between community structure and specific soil processes is commonly found in literature to be non-linear due to the complexity of the interaction among the microbial consortia (Stres and Tiedje, 2006). On the contrary, while new technologies are increasing the number of enzymes used to assess soil function (Bardelli et al., 2017; Fornasier et al., 2015), it is still very difficult to link enzymes to specific soil microbes in order to assess and understand their functional role.

Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes are the most abundant fungi in the upper soil layer (Grinhut et al., 2007). In addition to their known structural differences in hyphae size and mycelium structure, which make them very efficient in nutrient uptake and soil aggregation (Yafetto, 2019), Basidiomycetes are generally considered more active in the degradation of lignin (Hatakka and Hammel, 2011) whereas Ascomycetes are primarily responsible for the degradation of plant cell wall polysaccharides (cellulose and hemicellulose, pectins). Indeed, both these phyla contribute jointly or sequentially to plant residue decomposition (Fukasawa, 2021; Li et al., 2022).

The functional properties of Basidiomycota and Ascomycota were compared using the enzymatic profile of pure fungal colonies representative of these two phyla. While realising that the functionality of soils is as much a result of the microorganisms as of their interactions, we started with single fungal colonies at standardized conditions to identify the basic differences of the two groups of microorganism more active in plant residues degradation and transformation of humic substances (Grinhut et al., 2007). The final objective was to find new elements for understanding the functional significance of phyla variations within soil.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Fungal isolates

Twenty-nine fungal isolates belonging to 26 different species were selected for this study (Table 1). All were saprotrophic fungi isolated in previous studies by incubating plant tissue fragments on water agar and then transferring hyphal tips to a common nutrient media. Fungal colonies were identified and stored as colony fragments or spore suspensions in 10% dimethyl sulfoxide water solution at -160°C under liquid N in the working collection of the CREA-AA in Bologna, Italy. (Table 1). All these pure colonies after isolation were sub cultured at least three times on a common nutrient media.

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Table 1. List of 29 fungal isolates belonging to with relevant accession numbers of the nucleotide sequence in GenBank <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/> or reference of the studies in which they are cited. Isolates from wood and soil-root (w and s in column 2, respectively)

		Sequence_ID	Organism	GenBank Accession n.
A [□]	w ^λ	Botri_dio01	<i>Botryosphaeria dothidea</i>	OQ060521
A	w	Botri_dio02	<i>Botryosphaeria dothidea</i>	OQ060522
A	w	Neocuc_s_a	<i>Neocucurbitaria salicis-albae</i>	OQ060549
A	w	Neofus_p01	<i>Neofusicoccum parvum</i>	OQ060550
A	w	parac_hak01	<i>Paraconiothyrium hakeae</i>	OQ060551
A	w	Neocuc_s_a	<i>Neocucurbitaria salicis-albae</i>	OQ060549
A	w	Dal_child01	<i>Daldinia childiae</i>	OQ060539
A	w	Dal_child02	<i>Daldinia childiae</i>	OQ060540
A	w	Diap_onc01	<i>Diaporthe oncostoma</i>	OQ060541
A	s	Tri_00	<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	OQ060558
A	s	Tri_atr01	<i>Trichoderma atroviride</i>	OQ060559
A	s	Clonost_ro01	<i>Clonostachys rosea</i>	OQ060528
A	s	Pcom_01	<i>Penicillium commune</i>	(Manici and Caputo, 2010)
A	s	Pver_01	<i>Penicillium verrucosum</i>	ISClf3 (Fila et al., 2001)
A	s	Cyl149	<i>Dactylonectria torresensis</i>	OL474341
A	s	Cyl161	<i>Dactylonectria pauciseptata</i>	OL474335
A	s	Cyl148	<i>Dactylonectria novozelandica</i>	OL474340
A	s	Thi_bas02	<i>Berkeleyomyces basicola</i>	GQ131878
A	s	Fox52	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	GQ131884
A	s	Fsem9	<i>Fusarium incarnatum</i>	KJ562368
A	s	Facu15	<i>Fusarium acuminatum</i>	(Manici et al., 2015)
A	s	Fav01	<i>Fusarium avenaceum</i>	(Manici et al., 2005)
B	w	RhizoAG-G	<i>Rhizoctonia</i> sp. AG-G	OL342354
B	w	Cond_cand01	<i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i>	OQ060529
B	w	Copr_dom01	<i>Coprinellus domesticus</i>	OQ060531
B	w	Copr_rad01	<i>Coprinellus radians</i>	OQ060533
B	w	Cor_diss01	<i>Coprinellus disseminatus</i>	OQ060538
B	w	Auric_au_ju01	<i>Auricularia auricula-judae</i>	OQ060520
B	w	Tram_tro01	<i>Trametes trogii</i>	OQ060556
B	w	Tram_tro02	<i>Trametes trogii</i>	OQ060557

[□] A and B indicate the isolate belonging to Ascomycota and Basidiomycota, respectively.

^λw (wood) and s (soil) indicate the original substrate from which isolation made

Basidiomycota were isolated from deadwood except binucleate *Rhizoctonia* which was isolated from roots (Table 1). Among Ascomycetes, thirteen were Deuteromycetes, or mitosporic fungi (Kiffer and Morelet, 2000), such as *Trichoderma*, *Penicillium* and *Clonostachys*, *Fusarium*, *Dactylonectria*, *Berkeleyomyces*, *Paraconiothyrium* spp which had been isolated from plant residues and roots; there was a *Diaporthe*. The other ascomycetes were isolated from dead and living wood: *Daldinia childiae* is a fungal degrader belonging to Xylariaceae (Stadler et al., 2014), *Botryosphaeria*, *Neofusicoccum* and *Neocucurbitaria*, belong to the complex of fungi responsible for trunk disease and tree decay (Halleen et al., 2007; Marsberg et al., 2017; Massonnet et al., 2017; Gutiérrez-Flores et al., 2020). Each frozen isolate was transferred for regeneration to PSA (Potato Sucrose Agar) in four 5 cm-dia. petri dishes and grown for 6-10 days at 24 ± 2 °C. A portion of the colony of approximately 3 cm² was taken from each plate and transferred to a 2 ml-Eppendorf and maintained at 4 °C up to the enzymatic analysis, which was performed within 7 days. In the case of some Deuteromycetes, such as *F. oxysporum*, growing into the substrate, the surface was scraped slightly; in all cases mycelial mass was gently homogenized by hand in each Eppendorf with sterile Pipette tips for Gilson® Pipetman.

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2.2. Enzyme activity

Table 2. List of enzyme activity tested on the pure fungal colonies of the isolates in Table 1

Acronym	Enzyme
acronym	enzyme
aryS	arylsulfatase [□]
alfaG	alpha-glucosidase ^λ
betaG	beta-glucosidase ^λ
alfa GAL	alpha-galactosidase ^λ
betaGAL	beta-galactosidase ^λ
alfaMAN	alpha-mannosidase ^λ
betaMAN	beta-mannosidase ^λ
cellulase	endo-glucanase ^λ
cell	cellobiohydrolase ^λ
xilo	xilosidase ^λ
arabin	arabinase ^λ
uroni	glucuronidase ^λ
chit	chitinase ^λ
APROT	aspecific protease ^{dz}
CBZ	serin-like protease ^{dz}
leu	leucine-aminopeptidase ^{dz}
arginin	arginin-aminopeptidase ^{dz}
acP	acid phosphomonoesterase [≠]
bisP	phosphodiesterase [≠]
piroP	pirophosphate-phosphodiesterase [≠]
alkP	alkaline phosphomonoesterase [≠]
nona	nonanoate-esterase [‡]
FDA	fluorescein diacetate hydrolysis [‡]
PEROX	peroxidase [†]

□S- cycle (Li and Sarah, 2003)

λ C-syle (Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022)(Greenfield et al., 2021)

dz N-cycle (Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022)

≠ P-cycle (Criquet and Braud, 2008)

‡ indicators of total microbial activity (Gan et al., 2022)

† lignin degradation and humification (Sinsabaugh, 2010)

A total of 116 samples (twenty-nine fungal isolates in four replicates) were first subjected to the analysis of double-stranded DNA (dsDNA).

This analysis was carried out starting from 0.4 g of mycelial mass taken from each of the four replicates per isolate and processed as described by Fornasier et al. (2014) The quantity of dsDNA was expressed as μg of DNA g^{-1} mycelial mass. Twenty-five enzyme activities (Table 2) were analysed starting from the 0.4 g of mycelial mass used for dsDNA. The fungal extracts were obtained as already described in Cardelli et al., (2019). Briefly, enzymes were extracted by heteromolecular exchange using a 3% lysozyme solution (Cowie et al., 2013); then their activities were quantified in microplates using fluorogenic substrates as reported in Supplementary materials Table S1. The evaluated enzyme activities were those most widely used to assess soil functionality variation in response to land use or changes in the environmental variables (Cardelli et al., 2019; Fanin et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2020). Enzymatic activity of each sample was first divided by its dsDNA value which enabled overcoming the error deriving from the difference in mycelial mass concentration existing between the fungal species.

2.3. Data analysis

Data analysis was carried out on $\ln(x+1)$ transformed data which were subjected to multivariate analysis using the PAST version 3.24 (Hammer et al., 2001), a software for analysis in

ecology. Permutational MANOVA (NPMANOVA), pairwise comparison, principal component analysis (PCA) and cluster analysis using Bray-Curtis distance and 9999 bootstrapping replicates were applied. Similarity percentage analysis (SIMPER) was used to assess which enzyme activities were primarily responsible for the significant difference between Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes (Clarke, 1993). The enzymatic profile of each isolate was obtained with an absence-presence matrix of enzyme activity concentrated diagonally according to Seriation (Brower et al., 1988) where, the different values of the same enzyme activity were represented with a three-level colour scale: (i) low (from traces up to 30% the maximum value observed of each enzyme); (ii) medium (from 31 to 60% of the maximum value observed); (iii) high (from 61% to 100% of the maximum value observed).

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3. Results and Discussion

Ascomycota and Basidiomycota differ greatly based on enzymatic profile of pure fungal colonies according to AMOVA ($P=0.0001$), and pairwise comparison ($P=0.0001$) confirmed this separation. Principal component analysis displayed samples (four replicated per each of 29 isolates) of Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes in two well separated groups ($P=0.05$) across two opposite quadrants of the XY plot (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Principal component analysis inferred from the enzyme profile (25 enzymes) of 29 fungal isolates in 4 replicates. Ellipses group samples at $P=0.05$

According to the SIMPER analysis (Table 3), all variables (25 enzyme activities) contributed to this differentiation among the two fungal phyla in a percentage ranging indicatively from 1 to 10% (Table 3). Alkaline phosphomonoesterase (alkP) and alpha-galactosidase (alfaGAL) were the two variables which mainly contributed to discriminating Ascomycota from Basidiomycota with a contribution of 10.6% and 6.98% respectively (Table 3); phosphodiesterase (bisP), beta-glucosidase (betaG) and other enzymes, including cellobiohydrolase (cell) and chitinase (chit) contributed more than 5% (Table 3).

Seven out of twenty-five enzyme activities recorded in Ascomycetes did not occur in Basidiomycetes, as shown in the seriation table (Fig. 2). Among these, only two enzymes of phosphorus metabolism (alkP and bisP) were among those contributing most to discriminating Ascomycetes from Basidiomycetes according to the SIMPER analysis (Table 3). The other five were one phosphorus and one sulphur enzyme (piroP and aryS) and three others of C-cycle (CBZ, arabin, cellulase) (Fig. 2). The larger P- and S-enzymatic pool of Ascomycota suggest that they can better cover phosphorous and sulphur metabolism than Basidiomycetes.

Table 3. SIMPER analysis (percent similarity) showing which enzymatic activities were primarily responsible for the observed difference between Ascomycetes vs Basidiomycetes.

Enzyme activity	Average dissimilarity	Contribution (%)	Cumulative (%)	Mean ASCOMYCOTA	Mean BASIDIOMYCOTA
alkP	3.5	10.64	10.64	5.32 [^]	0.58
alfaGAL	2.3	6.98	17.62	3.52	2.96
bisP	1.88	5.71	23.33	2.96	0.46
betaG	1.88	5.71	29.04	6.51	4.27
cell	1.8	5.47	34.51	2.94	0.96
chit	1.78	5.41	39.92	6.74	4.42
betaGAL	1.71	5.20	45.12	3.00	2.85
arginin	1.51	4.59	49.71	4.63	2.84
Av. of the other 17	0.971	2.45	50.29 [¥]	3.00	2.18

[¥]cumulative % of the 17 other enzyme

[^]Mean of the ln(x+1) transformed original values

The plant polysaccharide degradation enzymes, including alpha-galactosidase (alfaGAL), beta-mannosidase (betaMAN) or xilosidase (xilo), which can degrade or modify these compounds (essentially cellulose, hemicellulose and pectin) for further degradation steps (Van Den Brink and De Vries, 2011), were largely shared by Ascomycota and Basidiomycota (Fig. 2). Alpha-galactosidase (alfaGAL) and endo-glucanase (cellulase) were absent in Basidiomycetes and the enzyme activity largely varied within each phylum (Fig. 2). Overall, these findings are consistent with the separation found between Ascomycota and Basidiomycota based on the gene expression for carbohydrate-active enzymes reported by (TIÁskal et al., 2021). However, the large and variable plant-polysaccharide-degrading found also in Basidiomycetes had been already observed by Rytioja et al. (2014), who suggested that this pool of enzymes is not a peculiarity of Deuteromycetes Ascomycota, though the latest are conventionally known as the most active in degrading herbaceous crop residues (Thygesen et al., 2003).

Albeit limited to the selection of fungal isolates in this study, it is possible to state that, based on enzyme pattern (Fig. 2), Ascomycetes have a wider enzymatic profile than Basidiomycetes. This finding is consistent with the recent study of de Vries et al. (2020) stating that recent insights made available by genome sequences revealed a much larger degrading potential in Ascomycetes than that was previously assumed. On the other hand, Basidiomycota represent the only phylum capable of totally degrading lignin (TIÁskal et al., 2021). To do this, Basidiomycota use a number of mechanisms which can vary from: secretion of peroxidases and laccases leading to the production of a pool of heterogeneous aromatics in the case of white rot fungi; employment of small molecule reactive types for depolymerizing lignin, without a ligninolytic enzyme, in the case of brown rot fungi (Cragg et al., 2015); to a complex process involving a joint action between bacteria and fungi in other cases (TIÁskal et al., 2021).

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Fig. 2. Absence-presence matrix of enzyme activity concentrated along the diagonal according to Seriation (Brower et al., 1988). The intensity of the enzyme activity was represented by a three-level colour scale (low, medium, and high), calculated based on the highest value of each enzyme activity.

* Agents of trunk disease and tree decline

Clustering of the fungal isolates based on enzyme pattern first confirmed the separation between Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes, with a similarity lower than 75% (Fig. 3). Second, it highlighted a large variability among the isolates, though previously subculturing fungal colonies on a common generic media should have reduced the influence of the original metabolic specialization of the isolates. In particular, Ascomycetes, with an intra-phylum similarity varying from 70 to 94%, were characterised by larger inter- and intra-genus variability as shown by the distribution of the mitosporic fungal species belonging to the *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*, *Dactylonectria* genera which did not cluster based on the taxonomic rank (Fig. 3). This finding was in line with the large differences in degrading ability of those mitosporic fungal genera (Deuteromycetes) which are the most active in crop residue degradation typically occurring in arable soils (Caesar-TonThat et al., 2010).

Again, within Ascomycetes, the agents of tree decline, such as *Daldinia*, *Botryosphaeria* or *Fusicoccum*, isolated from wood appeared clearly separated from the other isolates (Deuteromycetes) (Fig. 3). Indeed, there was a significant difference between these two functional groups of Ascomycota according to AMOVA ($P < 0.0001$). The variable that most influenced this differentiation were the plant polysaccharide degrading enzymes such as beta-galactosidase (betaGAL), alpha-galactosidase (alfaGAL), and alpha-glucosidase (alfaG), thus suggesting that wood degradation mechanisms of the tree decay agents differ from those of Basidiomycota and confirms the greater plasticity of the Ascomycota metabolic pool. Finally, interestingly but unsurprisingly, as it has also been widely found in Ascomycetes (Liers et al., 2011), peroxidase, which is an oxidative enzyme component of the lignin-degrading enzyme system, was detected equally in Ascomycetes and Basidiomycetes.

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Fig. 3. Similarity in enzyme profile between the 29 isolates. Clustering using UMPGA method, Bray-Curtis distance and 1000 bootstrap replicates.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study confirm the general difference in functional characteristics between ascomycetes and basidiomycetes, not only in relation to carbon cycling, but also to overall soil functionality. Based on the enzymatic profile, Ascomycetes have a greater capacity to adapt to organic residues of different origin and different host plants than Basidiomycetes. On the other hand, the lower intra-gene variability of the enzyme pattern observed in Basidiomycetes (Fig. 3) suggests more stable functional properties that genera of this phyla may have achieved to successfully degrade lignin and recalcitrant materials. Although the observed differences between Ascomycota and Basidiomycota in the enzyme pattern is a new insight in interpreting their importance for soil functionality, their different reproductive patterns and dispersal into the soil, as well as their morphological characteristics have to be always taken into consideration. Indeed, Basidiomycota, with their extensive branching mycelial network (rhizomorphs) should not be underestimated for soil binding properties (Caesar-TonThat et al., 2010) as well as for their well-known highest capacity to accumulate carbon and all nutrient elements (Šnajdr et al., 2011).

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Supplementary material.

Table S1. List of the enzyme with the relevant substrate and the activity expression

Acronym	enzyme	substrate	enzyme activity
aryS	arylsulfatase	4-methylumbelliferyl sulfate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
alfaG	alpha-glucosidase	4-methylumbelliferyl-alpha-D-glucopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
betaG	beta-glucosidase	4-methylumbelliferyl-beta-D-glucopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
alfaGAL	alpha-galactosidase	4-Methylumbelliferyl-alpha-D-galactopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
betaGAL	beta-galactosidase	4-Methylumbelliferyl-beta-D-galactopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
alfaMAN	alpha-mannosidase	4-Methylumbelliferyl-alpha-D-mannopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
betaMAN	beta-mannosidase	4-Methylumbelliferyl-beta-D-mannopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
cellulase	endo-glucanase	4-methylumbelliferyl-beta-D-tri-glucopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
cell	cellobiohydrolase	4-methylumbelliferyl beta-D-cellobioside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
xilo	xilosidase	4-methylumbelliferyl beta-D-xilopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
arabin	arabinase	4-Methylumbelliferyl-alpha-L-arabinopyranoside	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
uroni	glucuronidase	4-methylumbelliferyl-beta-D-glucuronide	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
chit	chitinase	4-methylumbelliferyl-N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminide	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
APROT	aspecific protease	fluorescein-labeled casein	fluorescence units
CBZ	serin-like protease	N-alpha-CBZ-L-Arginine 7-amido-4-methylcoumarin hydrochloride	nanomoles of 7-amino-4methyl coumarine)* g-1 dry soil* hour-1
leu	leucine-aminopeptidase	L-Leucine 7-amido-4methyl-coumarine hydrochloride	nanomoles of 7-amino-4methyl coumarine)* g-1 dry soil* hour-1
arginin	arginin-aminopeptidase	L-Arginine 7-amido-4-methylcoumarin	nanomoles of 7-amino-4methyl coumarine)* g-1 dry soil* hour-1
acP	acid phosphomonoesterase	4-methylumbelliferyl phosphate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
bisP	phosphodiesterase	bis(4-methylumbelliferyl)phosphoric acid	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
piroP	pirophosphate-phosphodiesterase	bis(4-methylumbelliferyl)pyrophosphoric acid	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
alkP	alkaline phosphomonoesterase	4-methylumbelliferyl phosphate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
inositP	phytase	4-methylumbelliferyl myo-inositol-1-phosphate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
nona	nonanoate-esterase	4-methylumbelliferyl nonanoate	nanomoles of 4-methylumbelliferone * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
FDA	fluorescein diacetate hydrolysis	5,6-carboxyfluorescein	nanomoles of 5,6carboxyfluorescein * g-1 dry soil* hour-1
peroxidase	peroxidase	10-Acetyl-3,7-dihydroxyphenoxazine + H2O2	picomoles of resorufin * g-1 dry soil* hour-2

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